

Date

January 12, 2026

PROJECT REPORT

Assessing AI Tools for Argumentation in Academic Writing in the Humanities and Social Sciences

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Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the Mphasis Lab for supporting this project, and Professors Shantanu Bhanja, Partha Pratim Chakrabarti, and Lipika Dey for their guidance, feedback, and sustained engagement in the course of this study. Their conversations were instrumental in shaping the project's direction and refining its scope. We also thank Professor Rintu Kutum for his insights and support in the process of hiring a Research Assistant for this project.

We're grateful for the contributions of our Research Assistant, Karnav, for helping us with the data cleaning, coding, and visualisations for this project, and for supporting our research and review processes.

We are grateful to our Director, Dr. Kanika Singh, for her support in facilitating the flexibility needed within our regular responsibilities at the Centre, which enabled us to carry this project to completion, her interest and support with our queries which helped us make this project a smooth process.

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1. INTRODUCTION

By its definition, the term ‘academic writing’, in general usage, and when referred to in this piece, implies the style of writing generally associated with modern academia across a wide range of different disciplines and fields of study. While these disciplines often operate with each having its own specialised set of terminologies and instances of specific word usages, they nevertheless share certain broad conventions of academic writing. These conventions have emerged through a long process of historical development, within the disciplinary boundaries of different streams of study, as well as within the broader institutional practices of the academy as a whole. This evolution has been driven by a gradual movement towards achieving greater clarity, precision, focus, ease of argumentation, well-structured organisation, and a streamlined presentation of ideas - features that serve both academic and pedagogic purposes. Although English is currently one of the most widely used languages in academic communication across the world, it is not the only language used within academic contexts. The general principles that define academic writing - such as coherence and reasoned argumentation - remain applicable regardless of the language in which academic work is produced. Finally, the scope of what comes under the ambit of ‘academic writing’ per se may also vary depending on the length, purpose, and context: a single reflective sentence written for a classroom discussion can qualify as academic writing just as much as a short essay for a classroom assignment, or a full-length doctoral dissertation. It is within this inclusive and broad understanding of academic writing, which includes both formal and informal academic tasks, that recent technological interventions in writing practices need to be situated and closely examined. This calls for an interrogation of how newly emerging writing tools shape the academic writing process across its various stages, including ideation, idea generation, structuring, and revision.

The prevalence of the usage of generative AI as an academic writing tool was largely coeval with the release and the subsequent prominence of the LLM platform ChatGPT from late 2022. Its swift adoption by students, teachers, and researchers across disciplines for varying needs and requirements brought AI-assisted writing into everyday academic practice in a relatively short span of time. A growing body of work highlights the varied purposes for which AI tools are used by students to aid them at different stages of the learning and writing process. For example, a study published on 6 October, 2025, looking at data from postgraduate students and research scholars from three universities in Kerala, India, identified different academic activities across disciplines for which certain popular free AI tools such as ChatGPT, Grammarly, and Quillbot were used. These included understanding and learning concepts, academic writing, grammar checking and paraphrasing. (Archana *et al.*) There are additional studies, such as “Perceptions of effectiveness and ethical use of AI tools in academic writing: A study among PhD scholars in India” (Subaveerapandiyan *et al.*) which are geared towards looking at the comparative effectiveness of leveraging AI tools versus traditional methods for tasks such as paraphrasing, plagiarism detection, and citation improvement.

Further, inquiries such as “Writing without borders: AI and cross-cultural convergence in academic writing quality” explore the evolution of academic writing quality in social sciences abstracts with a primary focus on disparities across linguistic, regional, economic and gender-based classifications. Here, the findings indicate a considerable improvement in writing

complexity, especially in the case of non-native English-speaking countries, linking these gains to structural factors, for instance, expanded internet access, and the increasing use of AI-based tools like LLMs. (Prakash *et al.*) Claire Miller similarly highlights the benefits of AI literacy, where these tools can help enhance argument quality and help in developing writing skills, which include a careful refinement of words and sentences for better coherence, clarity, and transition. This also includes idea generation, literature synthesis, enhanced specificity of claims, logical coherence, incorporation of rebuttals, and editing. (Raza *et al.*; Khalifa and Albadawy). At the same time, however, research has indicated how an overreliance on AI tools as efficient shortcuts can impact students' cognitive competence considerably, including decision-making, critical thinking, and analytical reasoning. (Zhai, Wibowo, and Li) Furthermore, studies (Rawan AlSaad *et al.*) also underline the dangers of the integration of false information into papers and how the lack of transparency in the training sets and LLMs can lead to misinformation, the incorporation of biases and inaccuracies. (Abd-alrazaq *et al.*)

In the absence of comprehensive regulatory frameworks, even though there is an urgent call for the same, whether at the level of individual institutions or international scholarly bodies, the advent of AI has become a significant inflection point, resulting in widespread ambivalence. Responses range from initial enthusiasm and optimism about increased efficiency and support to scepticism, ethical concern, and apprehension. These anxieties continue to persist and are manifest in ongoing debates surrounding authorship, originality, accountability, and the potential erosion of core values of academic integrity. While a large part of this debate is positioned at the level of policy and ethics, it is equally significant to inspect how these concerns are experienced and sought to be negotiated in everyday academic practice. Writing centres, in particular, given their direct engagement with students' writing processes, challenges, and habits, offer a unique vantage point from which to analyse the practical implications of AI-assisted writing.

At the Centre for Writing and Communication (CWC), Ashoka University, a dedicated writing centre within a liberal arts institution situated in the Delhi National Capital Region, we offer writing support to the academic community. We provide one-on-one consultation (45 mins - 1 hour) sessions to help students with different aspects of academic writing, ranging from ideation and brainstorming to restructuring, fine-tuning and revising for focus and clarity. These sessions are largely oriented towards encouraging sustained engagement with writing as a reflective and recursive process rather than being a purely outcome-driven task. The three members of the present project team have been affiliated with the CWC for periods ranging from three to eight years. Since 2022, we've discovered a large dependence on Artificial Intelligence (henceforth AI) tools amongst the student community. This is visible in the inconsistencies in writing style and tone, and the formation and progression of the arguments, culminating from a lack of rigorous engagement with existing scholarship. Such patterns emerge during consultations where students often struggle to clearly articulate their argumentative choices or demonstrate ownership over the structure and claims of their writing. This overreliance on AI tools can be seen as impeding rather than facilitating the learning process, where the student can, with trial and error, come to develop academic writing skills. Such concerns underline the importance of examining AI usage not solely through regulatory or ethical perspectives but also through lived academic practice. Writing centres, as sites offering a sustained engagement with student writing, offer a promising ground for

such an inquiry.

It is in this context that we conducted an experiment to determine the impact of using AI on argumentative academic writing. The experiment involved 30 students writing 71 argumentative essays (500 words) responding to a curated list of prompts from disciplines such as English, Sociology, Political Science, History, and International Relations. The logs of the students' chats with the LLMs were also recorded. This was done in a controlled setting where one stage had them write their responses without any AI-assistance, where they were free to look up other credible sources online, and the other allowed for writing assisted by any AI tool of their choosing. The quantitative and qualitative analysis of the data set was done using the following four parameters: Introduction (to assess how effectively the topic and central thesis are introduced), Claims and Evidence (to evaluate the strength and relevance of the claims made and the quality of supporting evidence), Argument Structure (to examine the logical flow of arguments, including the use of counterarguments and supporting points, and analyse how they contribute to or reinforce the main argument), and Academic Style (to gauge whether analysis is written in a formal academic style avoiding conversational language, contractions, and colloquialisms.)

The report that follows details our methodology, presents an analysis of the data, and advances some recommendations on pedagogically responsible integration of generative AI within higher education, with a view towards preserving the rigours of academic composition in an era of algorithmic augmentation.

Our project, in focusing on the chosen parameters and how they are impacted by AI usage, aims to contribute meaningfully to the evolving discourse on AI's role in the context of South Asian academia. The comparative analysis of student papers written with and without AI assistance aims to investigate how students engage with AI in the process of writing, how this affects the argumentative nature of what they produce as the end product, and what lessons can educators and writers learn from this exercise. By examining the depth of engagement with AI-generated content and its impact on the overall quality of writing, the objective here is to identify best practices for leveraging AI as a useful tool for enhancing academic writing skills. We anticipate that our findings will have wide-ranging implications, significantly shaping how reading and writing are understood within the humanities and social sciences.

Methodology

The study used a series of controlled experiments followed by a multipronged analytical approach that combined qualitative and quantitative methods. The experiments were preceded by a brief orientation session to outline the guidelines, underline key concepts in argumentative writing, such as claims supported by evidence and academic tone, along with an overview of prompt engineering. Student essays were assessed by both human evaluators and AI systems using predefined rubrics, alongside linguistic and word-level analysis. The methodology integrated qualitative grading, quantitative scoring, parts-of-speech analysis, and word-to-word metrics, as well as LLM-based structural and argument mapping, to examine the differences between AI-assisted and non-AI writing.

Experiment and Data

The methodology employed a controlled experimental design involving 30 undergraduate students from Ashoka University, who participated in 12 sessions conducted between March and May 2025, producing a total of 84 essays (47 unaided and 37 AI-assisted) of approximately 560 words each. Participants were divided into two groups, completing four essays: two with AI support and two without, responding to prompts drawn from six disciplines (Sociology and Anthropology, Political Science, International Relations, English Literature, History and Economics). AI-assisted sessions permitted access to generative tools, with 21 complete chat logs collected for further analysis, while non-AI sessions were restricted to such access. Essays were anonymised and subjected to an evaluation framework using a qualitative rubric-based grading system by human assessors, parts-of-speech tagging to map analytical components, and quantitative word-to-word metrics, to draw insights into writing quality, stylistic features, and argumentative structures between AI-assisted and independent compositions.

Analysis

Four sets of analyses were conducted on the essays to capture differences in writing quality, linguistic features, and argumentative organisation. First, a qualitative assessment was carried out through two parallel processes: human evaluation by the project team and LLM-based evaluation. Both approaches assessed the same four dimensions: introduction, claims and evidence, argument structure, and academic style. In parallel, quantitative scoring assigned cumulative scores to each essay, enabling systematic comparison across AI-assisted and non-AI conditions.

Second, word-level quantitative analysis focused on identifying linguistic and rhetorical patterns across essays. Metrics such as lexical diversity, evidence-to-hypothesis ratio, frequency of first-person pronouns, analytical verb density, hedging language, and modal verb use were calculated to assess authorial presence, objectivity, and analytical depth.

Finally, structural and argument mapping were conducted using an LLM-based, two-stage approach that combines unsupervised and semi-supervised sentence-level annotation. Essays were mapped into argumentation graphs that modelled relationships between claims, evidence, reasoning, and conclusions at both sentence and higher-order levels. These visual and quantitative representations were used to examine cohesion, density, and organisational patterns in argumentative writing, and to test whether AI-assisted essays exhibited greater homogeneity or rigidity compared to essays written without AI support.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

AI Adoption in Academic Writing Contexts

2.1 Patterns of Use and AI Literacy: Benefits and Limitations

The proliferation and growing usage of LLMs like ChatGPT in academic writing in a university context is symptomatic of a significant advancement in the integration of technology into the process of academic writing, both academic and otherwise. Several significant studies identify and investigate popular AI tools and investigate the different purposes for which they are used in an academic context, both by students to help them with various writing tasks and requirements, and by teachers for devising lesson plans and modes of assessment. At the same time, there is an increasing urgency being placed on how to ensure ethical and responsible use of AI.

Within this broader empirical landscape, studies such as the one conducted by Zakir Hossain, Nadim Akhtar Khan *et al.*, in their survey of participants from Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan, examine disparities in AI literacy and note that while English language competency was found to impact familiarity and understanding of AI tools, it did not influence overall proficiency. They observe that AI tools are primarily used for academic tasks, which include searching for information, proofreading and summarisation and advocate for targeted interventions to ensure greater ethical awareness. Additionally, other areas where AI has been seen to be productively leveraged include assistance with tasks such as outline preparation, content revision, proofreading, post-writing reflection, enhanced writing fluency and a reduction in the cognitive load of drafting and revising. (Su, Lin, and Lai; Das Deep and Chen)

Extending this line of inquiry, the review conducted by Mohamed Khalifa and Mona Albadawy, in looking at the manner in which AI tools can act as aids in academic writing, identifies six primary domains: helping with idea generation and research design, improving content and organisation, supporting literature review and synthesis, augmenting data management and analysis, assisting in editing and review, and providing assistance with communication and ethical compliance. The recommendations offered point towards a broader integration of AI tools in academia, ensuring ethical and transparent use, and establishing a balance between AI and human use. (Khalifa and Albadawy) In a related vein, S. N. Archana, V. R. Renjith, P. K. Padmakuma *et al.*, in their structured questionnaire administered to students and scholars across Science, Social Science, and Technology disciplines, reported that different academic purposes for which AI tools are being used include learning and understanding, and literature review. The study notes that university students, irrespective of their disciplinary orientation, widely use AI tools for most of their academic activities and finds a significantly higher likelihood of AI tool usage by the Social Science students, which it ties to the subjective nature of the discipline and the focus on literature review for research. The study finds its findings aligned with similar inquiries conducted in India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka. (Archana *et al.*)

Moving from usage patterns to practice-oriented engagement, and investigating the usefulness of AI for supporting the research writing process, *Writing Your Thesis with ChatGPT* by Paul

Johannesson focuses on prompt engineering for thesis writing, offering prompts for finding research questions, conducting a literature review, collecting and analysing data, as well as helping with critical thinking and academic writing style. The book emphasises AI's role as a thinking partner and not an author, offering useful tips for refining prompts to achieve more accurate and relevant results while maintaining academic integrity and adhering to one's institution's guidelines on responsible AI use. Similarly, Gwo-Jen Hwang and Nian-Shing Chen emphasise the need for fostering teachers' and students' competences of programming prompts such as conversational prompts, content analysis prompts, and multimodal prompts. Their research finds that mastering the knowledge of these prompts would significantly affect the quality of GAI-based teaching and learning, including the quality of assessment plans, learning content and designs. (Hwang and Chen)

Complementing these instructional and research-oriented approaches, in the same line, we have other studies which are invested in looking at the role of Artificial Intelligence from students' perspectives, considering both benefits, such as personalised support, improved accessibility, an enhancement in clarity, flow and efficiency, as well as drawbacks, which include concerns over overreliance, originality, ethical transparency, and disengagement. These inquiries also offer practical solutions, which include AI-driven competitions and tailored tools for diverse learners. (Homer *et al.*; Subaveerapandiyan, Kalbande, and Ahmad) However, limitations have been found at different levels of argumentation including process, reasoning, and expression, where the generated content was found to have weaknesses indicating that the generation of persuasive and well-reasoned argumentation emerges as a more difficult task compared to the production of meaningful language. This was done using the Comprehensive Assessment Procedure for Natural Argumentation (CAPNA) in evaluating the arguments produced by an Artificial Intelligence text generator, GPT-3, in an opinion piece written for the *Guardian* newspaper in 2020. (Hinton and Wagemans)

2.2 Pedagogical Models and Technology Adoption Frameworks

The pedagogical discourse on AI assistance begins with foundational frameworks that model its adoption, often drawing from established theories like the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). These models provide a scaffold for understanding how AI tools might support academic writing, but they also highlight several barriers in developing regions like India. Sabiteka *et al.*, for instance, proposed the Educational Technology Adoption for Developing Countries (ETADC) model, which assimilated key markers such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, price value, and facilitating conditions within the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework. This model concludes that affordability and infrastructure are key to sustainable application and integration of EdTech in resource-constrained settings, advocating for context-sensitive approaches that could extend to AI-assistance, where low-cost tools like ChatGPT might promise to bridge digital divides but can also require teacher-training for nuanced guidance (Sabiteka *et al.*).

Extending this critical evaluation of adoption models, Al-kfairy conduct a review of forty empirical

studies, observing factors such as hedonic motivation, usability, and perceived benefits influencing ChatGPT adoption in higher education, through models like TAM and UTAUT (Al-kfairy). Humble and Mozelius's important study around the hyped expectations of Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED) and its potential to transform present educational systems, identified AI's strengths in efficiency for language tasks but noted its weaknesses, including concerns around quality education and algorithmic biases, which pose a challenge to traditional teacher-student relationships (Humble and Mozelius).

From a pedagogical standpoint, studies note an improved support for teachers in answering student questions and where recommendations underline the significance of using a blended instructional approach where AI is utilised for accuracy alongside traditional instruction for cultivating learning skills, collaborative peer-review exercises, and policies to encourage transparency and ethical use. (Su, Jiahong *et al.*) In the Indian context, Sharma and Yadav positioned ChatGPT as a remedy for various educational challenges in India, advocating responsible use in teaching and learning to balance its advantages with the accompanying disruptions to traditional pedagogy (Sharma and Yadav).

Turning to questions of personalisation and learner experience, Michel-Villarreal *et al.* employed the concept of “thing ethnography” to interview ChatGPT itself. This method can primarily be read as an attempt to humanise AI, portraying it as a collaborative partner that complements human instructors, though limited by specialised discipline-specific expertise (Michel-Villarreal *et al.*). On a similar note, Kasneci *et al.* surveyed large language models' applications in higher education, presenting some potential benefits and challenges of educational applications of large language models, and argued that “... large language models in education require teachers and learners to develop set of competencies and literacies necessary to both understand the technology as well as their limitations and unexpected brittleness of such systems” highlighting that the need for systematic strategisation and clarity in pedagogical approach are key to integrating and taking full advantage of large language models in higher education and teaching curricula (Kasneci *et al.*).

2.3 AI-Mediated Practices in EFL instruction

Shifting the focus to instructional outcomes, in the context of examining the impact of (AI) technologies, particularly ChatGPT, and exploring how it is revolutionising academic writing instruction in the context of English as a Foreign Language (EFL), a quantitative analysis using a mixed methods framework noted a significant improvement in overall writing performance, with the most notable being in argument construction, evidence integration, and academic voice. The study was based on a comparative analysis of the participants' first and fifth drafts as pre-test and post-test assessments, and used an adapted AIAS framework which considered parameters such as content, organisation, language use, and critical thinking. (Deane *et al.*)

From a classroom practice perspective, in observing how applications like Quillbot, WordTune, Jenni, Chat-GPT, Paperpal, Copy.ai, and Essay Writer were being used in an EFL learning environment, Marzuki *et al.* note that AI writing tools, in addition to improving grammar and syntax, positively improved students' writing quality, particularly enhancing the quality of their

content and organization ensuring a smooth flow of ideas and connecting ideas in a logical and coherent manner.

Wei's mixed-methods study in China demonstrated how AI platforms could boost English learning achievement and self-regulated learning, with qualitative insights highlighting reduced anxiety through flexible practice among learners, concluding that AI-mediated language instruction could radically change language teaching and learning. Grassini framed the "new AI gold rush," where ChatGPT automates grading and generates tailored resources, freeing educators for more innovative tasks, but also noted concerns over its potential to "reduce analytical skills and promote misconduct". Similarly, Boubker's study in Morocco found social influence and ease of use, like self-learning features and personalised feedback, to be the main causes driving ChatGPT's adoption in education, gathering data through an online questionnaire and processing it through a "partial least squares technique". The study further highlighted that "ChatGPT perceived usefulness positively influences ChatGPT use, and students' satisfaction" suggesting a reiterative social loop.

2.4 Cognitive Risks and Overreliance

At the same time, however, critical concerns emerge around sustained AI use. Overreliance on AI tools is seen to impact cognitive abilities, with individuals favouring fast solutions and efficient shortcuts. These abilities are seen to include critical thinking and analytical reasoning competence. In the light of emerging challenges owing to factors such as misinformation and algorithmic biases, risk of misinformation, lack of originality and innovation, studies such as by Zhai *et al.* argue in favour of addressing these ethical concerns by integrating critical media literacy into curricula. Other proposed solutions include providing clarity to students regarding the difference between text generation (tasks such as writing, editing, and paraphrasing) and idea generation (linked to creativity) with an accompanying explanation underlining the importance of learning these skills independently rather than using AI as a replacement for mastering the core fundamentals of academic writing and engagement. (Vargas-Murillo; Cotton *et al.*)

2.5 AI and Academic Integrity: Ethical Safeguards and Policy Responses

Correspondingly, in the context of academic integrity, the commonality that emerges from different studies is that they all advocate against unbridled adoption of AI in higher education and academic writing contexts to preserve academic integrity. Several studies have cautioned against plagiarism undetectable by tools and the erosion of critical thinking, recommending AI-proof assessments like oral presentations, as well as training and support to users and using different methods to detect and prevent academic dishonesty, in the context of the proactive roles that universities and academic institutions should take for an ethical approach to the usage of AI tools (Cotton *et al.*). The Center for Teaching Excellence at the University of Kansas advises similar cautious use of AI detectors like Turnitin, citing high error margins, advocating several measures like allowing a second chance to the student and engaging substantially with the students' perspectives to gauge a case of academic dishonesty. The University of Calgary library guide has

listed several up-to-date and helpful resources for ethical AI use in academic writing. Another study by Shidiq, which focuses on creative writing but extends implications to argumentative tasks, argues that although the ease offered by ChatGPT may provide many conveniences, it diminishes originality and creativity, often resulting in superficial engagement. Similarly, Alasgarova and Rzayev applied Self-Determination Theory to Azerbaijani high school students noting that AI misuse fostered often extrinsic motivation and plagiarism in writing, advocating for careful consideration of “ethical use, digital literacy, and the cultivation of intrinsic motivation”.

At the policy and governance level, UNESCO’s article on Asia-Pacific education, a region composed of countries with varying levels of technological readiness, pointed at regional disparities, where AI’s misuse in writing assignments risks homogenisation of opinions and widening digital divides, alongside an erosion of critical thinking (Wang/UNESCO). In terms of teachers’ motivation, it has been noted by scholars that finding autonomy-supportive leadership actualises AI valuing and integration, where “... genAI valuing was associated with greater genAI integration in both teaching-related work and student learning activities” (Collie and Martin). Joyner’s study questioned ChatGPT as “partner or pariah,” narrating its resemblance to past technologies, especially calculators in mathematical education and using it to predict generative AI’s future impact on education, arguing that a “hysteria” around this new technology’s implications in educational settings, although avoidable rationally, is prevalent.

Consequently, the arrival of artificial intelligence (AI) in the higher education landscape has prompted a surge of policy discourse, as educators, institutions, and policymakers grapple to keep pace with technological innovation and to balance this innovation with concerns about integrity.

Nguyen *et al.* articulated a comprehensive set of ethical principles derived from international bodies such as UNESCO and the OECD, emphasising governance, transparency, privacy, security, inclusiveness, sustainability, and human-centred design as core principles for integrating AI into higher education. These principles, aimed towards serving as a framework to inform and guide various stakeholders in the higher education landscape, advocate for AI systems that complement rather than supplant human agency. On a similar note, Corrêa *et al.* reviewed 200 global AI governance guidelines, identifying consensus on principles like privacy protection, non-discrimination, and transparency. However, Munn critiqued such ethical frameworks as “useless,” arguing they are ambiguous, disconnected from industry practices, and lacking enforcement mechanisms, and thus failing to address the racial, social, and environmental disruptions caused by AI technologies. Al-kfairy *et al.* extended this perspective, highlighting ethical challenges in generative AI, including authorship ambiguity and intellectual property issues. They stress the importance of formulating policies, guidelines and frameworks that “... prioritise human rights, fairness, and transparency.” They proposed solutions like watermarking AI-generated content and updating integrity policies to require disclosure, and called for a multidisciplinary conversation around AI among policymakers, technologists and researchers.

Institutional responses further reinforce this trend, focusing on how universities can regulate AI to foster equitable and ethical use. Jin *et al.* provide a global analysis of 40 universities’ adoption policies for generative AI. They highlighted guidelines promoting AI literacy training, clear

communication channels, stakeholder collaboration, authenticity assessments to deter misuse, etc., but noted gaps in data privacy and access equity. In the Indian context, Gupta *et al.* proposed regulatory revisions by the University Grants Commission, mandating AI detection tools like Turnitin and ethical disclosure in academic submissions. Their policy recommendations include penalty structures for over-reliance on AI, such as grade reductions for undisclosed use, and literacy workshops to teach responsible integration. Similarly, Malik *et al.* examined Asian university policies, identifying promising practices like collaborative guideline development but gaps in addressing cultural contexts. Natarajan and Murali outline regulatory needs for AI in South Asia, advocating sector-specific guidelines to address biases in data pipelines that could skew AI-assisted outputs. They called for institutional safeguards like model certification and digital literacy programmes to ensure equitable use, contrasting South Asia's gaps with advanced frameworks.

Focusing on Bangladesh, Islam *et al.* explored ChatGPT's impact on higher education, calling for policies that promote equitable integration through access, training, and responsible usage. They argued that without such interventions, AI could widen educational divides, where students in resource-limited settings might overly rely on tools for content generation, sacrificing integrity.

An important issue concerns AI's influence on student agency in argumentative writing, where policies must balance assistance with skill development. Darvishi *et al.* investigated this through experiments, finding that AI prompts enhanced feedback but fostered reliance, diminishing self-regulation. They recommended hybrid policies combining AI with checklists to preserve agency. Awang Jambol *et al.*'s bibliometric review identified trends in ethical governance of AI-generated content, urging policies that address implications for academic writing. Mhlanga evaluated ChatGPT's value in learning environments, stressing ethical deployment to enhance accessibility while mitigating harms. Similarly, Suswanto *et al.* analysed ChatGPT's cross-field impacts, recommending updated training and assessment policies.

2.6 Responsible Use and Relevance of AI in Academic Writing Instruction

There appears to be a consensus on the transformative yet precarious role of AI in academic writing and higher education, necessitating policies and pedagogical approaches that mainly emphasise ethics, equity and agency. As noted in the review conducted by Hind Aljuaid, while universities like Stanford, the University of California, and Middlebury College can be seen to have updated their policies around AI usage and academic integrity over concerns about their potential impact on critical thinking competence and writing skills, this is not seen as AI tools supplanting university academic writing courses. This is because these courses are seen to play a significant role in cultivating students' analytical reasoning, interpretive abilities, research, and communication abilities - skills that extend beyond the scope of automated writing functions. Academic writing requires higher-order competencies such as contextualisation, synthesising sources, argument formulation, and adhering to disciplinary conventions. While AI supports functions such as grammar correction, restructuring/reorganising/rephrasing, and the generation of introductory text, it cannot replace the deep comprehension and analytical and argumentative

rigour that writing courses are designed to foster, where the emphasis is on foregrounding innovative thinking, persuasive reasoning, and responsible citation practices.

The discourse around the ethical and responsible deployment of AI in academia calls not simply for restriction but for a carefully calibrated and tailored use. The argument here is in favour of viewing AI as a useful supplementary aid rather than replacements for human-guided writing instruction, which prioritises the cultivation of advanced academic skills beyond AI's current capabilities. AI is seen to productively support learning, scaffold the thinking process, while helping reduce certain burdens. Care needs to be taken that this engagement is done in a manner which simultaneously preserves human agency, critical competence, and originality. When positioned as an assistive tool rather than a cognitive substitute, AI can boost efficiency and access without necessarily undermining academic integrity. Such a balanced approach foregrounds responsible use as an ethical practice in itself, which aids in integrating technological capabilities with pedagogical values while affirming the centrality of human reasoning and judgement, creativity, and accountability in scholarly domains.

2.7 Rubrics for Assessing Academic Writing

At a basic level, a rubric helps list criteria and gauge different levels of quality. These can range from scoring rubrics used exclusively for assigning grades or instructional rubrics which are co-created with students, used to facilitate peer-assessment, self-assessment and teacher feedback and only then used to assign grades. In the latter case, the rubric functions as more than just an evaluation tool but has more to do with teaching. (Andrade). Different criteria and evaluative frameworks are used in classrooms to summatively and formatively assess student agency in writing, connecting this to different objectives and audiences. Writing rubrics for argumentative writing, as Dobbs *et al* point out, can include the following components: Focus on Topic (Content), Sequencing (Organisation), Commitment (Voice), Word Choice, Sentence Structure (Sentence Fluency), and Grammar and Spelling (Conventions).

Building on these foundational understandings of rubric design, reviewing relevant literature on essay writing rubrics using the Delphi Technique (Mahdi and Alkhateeb) reveals a consistent set of core criteria across multiple studies, which form a consistent foundation for a comprehensive writing assessment that includes content and organisation, grammar and language use, vocabulary, and mechanics and conventions. Certain rubrics include more specific elements, such as voice and tone, sentence complexity, stance taking, and lexical tightness. While terminology and specific focus areas vary across rubrics, these core elements form a consistent foundation for comprehensive writing assessment, balancing both technical and creative aspects of essay writing. In order to assess essays that might be generated with AI tools, three additional criteria are also proposed - contextual relevance (to measure how well the essays adhere to the prompts), creativity and originality, and critical thinking.

Extending this discussion to AI-mediated writing contexts, existing scholarship on AI assistance in argumentative writing has demonstrated the use of a wide array of rubrics in order to quantify academic writing quality, contrasting AI-assisted and non-AI-assisted outputs. In a second

In a second language context, IELTS-based rubrics, for instance, emphasise task achievement, coherence, lexical resource, and grammatical accuracy (Waseem and All Song and Song; Cheng and Gong). Adaptations of Oshima and Hogue's scoring framework, which incorporated criteria for content development, cohesion, etc., on a 70-point scale, revealed significant improvements in ESL argumentative essays through AI integration with instructional models like WWIM (Writing Workshop Instructional Model) (Jaramillo *et al.*). Pre-AI rubrics, like those which integrated plagiarism detectors with holistic assessments of writing traits like ideas, organisation, and conventions, actually provide the baselines for non-AI quality measurement (Razi). AI tools might aid in rubric development itself, leading to some extent to pedagogical innovation in assessment design (Fernández-Sánchez). Rubrics for AI education effectiveness, though not exclusively writing-focussed, offer transferable metrics for learning outcomes in K-12 settings, which assess knowledge application and critical thinking via analytical scales (Kobara *et al.*).

More specifically, within studies focusing on AI-assisted essays, rubrics tailored for AI-assisted essays, such as those derived from Delphi techniques using nine criteria, including originality and critical thinking, also mainly address EFL contexts (Hmoud *et al.*). Models like Culham's 6+1 Traits, mainly emphasise AI's strengths in structure, grammar, and vocabulary while noting gaps in personal voice and idea precision (Cerón Urzúa *et al.*). Some other rubrics measuring critical writing, organisation and language on 0-100 scales, demonstrate AI's superiority in organisation and content (Zhang; Lo *et al.*). In comparative studies, rubrics adapted for L2 writing samples revealed AI's lenient biases and moderate agreement with human assessments, measured through metrics like weighted Kappas and ICC (intraclass correlation coefficient) (Geçkin *et al.*; Manning *et al.*; Tate *et al.*; Awidi). Conceptual frameworks for AI feedback literacy also allow for further refinements in rubrics by focusing on the interpretation capabilities of the learners, extended to oral analogues by Salvador-Cisneros *et al.*, but applicable to writing feedback utilisation (Salvador-Cisneros *et al.*).

Specific other parameters are also used when comparing human-written versus ChatGPT-generated essays. In their comparative analysis, Herbold *et al.* focused on the following six linguistic characteristics: lexical diversity (identifying vocabulary richness), sentence complexity (depth and clauses) nominalisation count (occurrences of nouns with suffixes such as '-ion', '-ment', '-ance'), presence of modals such as 'definitely' and 'potentially', and epistemic markers. ('I think', 'it is believed' and 'in my opinion').

At the level of providing feedback - both AI-generated (GPT-4) and from human tutors - studies such as Escalante *et al.* in examining the learning outcomes of university English as a new language (ENL) learners also deploy an analytic rubric assessing four key writing areas, namely content, coherence, language use, and sources and evidence. Using the participants' 300-word paragraph centered around diverse academic topics, comments are provided on areas such as the topic sentence, the development of ideas, language affecting the academic quality of the writing, the use of transitional phrases, the use of sources and evidence, and the grammatical accuracy of the language of the writing. In a similar vein, the University of British Columbia, Vancouver Campus, as part of their 'Evaluating AI Text' activity, shares a rubric that requires the students to check their 5-paragraph essay written on a topic of their interest using a rubric which includes checking

for accuracy, relevance, clarity, coherence, contextual understanding, bias, and sources and citations.

2.8 Contribution to Existing Scholarship

While existing scholarship has extensively examined the impact of AI tools on academic writing, ranging from ideation support and surface-level linguistic enhancement to entire content generation, much of this work has either relied on broad, holistic scoring frameworks or has foregrounded overall writing quality over the assessment of specific argumentative sub-components. Our study aims to contribute to this field by offering a systematic, component-level analysis of argumentative writing, explicitly differentiating between human-written and AI-assisted academic texts. This is geared towards better comprehending how AI assistance impacts different structural elements of academic argumentation. Furthermore, this study contributes methodologically by making explicit the manner of data collection and the analytical process.

From a methodological standpoint, the project rests on a clear delineation of assessment criteria, which is grounded in established rubric scholarship in composition studies, second language writing, and computational linguistics. By synthesising findings from Delphi-based rubric development studies, L2 argumentative writing frameworks and comparative analyses of human vs LLM-generated texts, this study provides a scaffolded rationale for the choice of its evaluative criteria. Specifically, the parameters chosen here draw upon a set of core criteria that recur across writing assessment literature, particularly organisation, and expression, which comprise a focus on Introduction, Claims and Evidence, Argument Structure and Academic Style. This positioning responds directly to recent calls within the field of AI-assisted writing research to move beyond treating the essay as a single evaluative unit or a sole emphasis on surface fluency and grammatical accuracy when evaluating LLM outputs. This analysis is further informed by a comparative computational linguistics focus on features such as lexical diversity and sentence complexity, which allows for a better distinction between human authorship and probabilistic text generation.

In an instructional context, the project is situated within the pedagogical context of the Centre for Writing and Communication, where tutor feedback targets distinct stages and components of academic writing, which include pre-writing, thesis statement articulation, claims and evidence, transition and flow, grammar and punctuation, and citation practices. By mapping these existing feedback categories onto a narrower set of analytically tractable parameters, the project seeks to bridge writing pedagogy and modes of assessing and analysing different aspects of academic writing in the context of AI usage. Given the time-frame for the project, the limitation to four focal parameters allows for a clearer and more focused observation while avoiding the pitfalls of overly broad rubrics. In doing so, the project aims to provide empirically grounded insights into how AI tools may differentially affect argumentative competence, thereby offering more targeted and pedagogically sound uses of LLMs in academic writing instruction.

3. METHODOLOGY

Experiments were conducted to collect data, followed by a multipronged analytical approach combining qualitative and quantitative assessment. Analyses included i) grading participants' writing by human and AI evaluators across predefined components (see Qualitative Rubric), ii) parts-of-speech tagging and mapping analytical components across full writing samples, and iii) measurement of word-to-word metrics (see Quantitative Rubric).

3.1 Experiment

A total of 30 undergraduate students from Ashoka University participated in a series of 12 experiments conducted between March and May 2025. Several students were current or former students of English-Language Teaching (ELT) courses offered by CWC. Approximately 50% of students were from first and second years, while the remaining were 3rd and final year students, in addition to 3 YIFs (Young India Fellows). 20 out of the 26 students who completed all rounds of the experiments described their major/minor: 9 students majored or minored in Economics, two of whom also studied International Relations; 4 students had a background in Sociology, 2 students had a background in English (one with English and Political Science), and one declared their major as History. 3 students listed their major/minor discipline as "other".

All participants attended a brief orientation session that outlined the experiment's rules, guidelines, and key concepts in analytical writing and prompt engineering. We emphasised structured academic writing: a clear introduction with an identifiable topic and central argument, claims supported by contextual evidence, a formal tone that avoids contractions and colloquialisms unless pertinent to the topic, and a conclusion that highlights stakes rather than only a summary of key points.

(Please refer to Appendix A for the detailed orientation plan.)

The project team included examples of how we would prefer students to approach experiment prompts. For example, in responding to "*How is AI being used in policing in modern society?*", students were encouraged to interpret "policing" and "modern society" expansively, grounding their argument in one or two well-developed examples in specific contexts, as multiple examples would render the essay overly descriptive. Each student wrote 4 essays total—2 with AI assistance, and 2 without. Participants were divided into 2 groups: one used AI support in the first set and not in the second, while the other followed the reverse order.

Prompts were drawn from 6 disciplines: Sociology/Anthropology, Political Science, International Relations, English Literature, History, and Economics. Students were free to respond to prompts outside their primary discipline, allowing the study to observe whether discipline-specific patterns of argumentation emerged across writing samples. Student essays were approximately 500 words each, and participants were given 1hr-1hr 15 minutes per essay for brainstorming and writing. During non-AI sessions, students used devices with access to popular AI tools blocked. For AI-assisted sessions, chat logs were collected at the end of the experiment (where available) for further analysis. 21 chat logs were analysed.

3.2 Data

The experiments yielded a set of 84 essays, comprising 47 written independently by students and 37 written with varying degrees of AI assistance¹. Although students were asked to write 500-word essays, the actual mean essay length was 560 words, with a standard deviation of 170 words. To enable fair comparative analysis, all essays were anonymised and converted to plain text. Among AI-assisted essays, only 64% (24 of 37) were accompanied by chat logs, of which 18 logs captured the complete dialogue history between students and AI. These logs include both student prompts and AI responses with timestamps. In a few cases, especially where students were browsing tools in guest mode (eg. stealthwriter.ai), we were unable to access chat logs as students exited the window without copying their chats. Despite this drawback, the dataset allowed us to examine differences in writing quality, stylistic quality, and argument structures in AI-assisted and non-AI essays.

3.3 Analysis

4 sets of analyses were performed on the essays.

A. Qualitative Assessment (Human and AI)

Each essay underwent two rounds of qualitative assessment. The project team graded four categories in each essay, assigning marks out of 3 for each:

- i) Introduction: clarity of thesis and fair topic contextualisation

- ii) Claims and evidence: presence and integration of appropriate evidence to support the argument. The writer's use of citations and evidence to support their argument was measured, differentiating between primary and secondary sources and noting their frequency and placement. A central component of this analysis was the effectiveness of text linking—how well evidence was woven into the narrative to support the argument. The sophistication of the essay's framing of evidence was assessed through the integration of historical, cultural, or social context. Citation practice was examined for density and rhetorical purpose (e.g., supporting, refuting, or building upon existing scholarship).

- iii) Argument structure: Coherence and progression of subarguments, presence of topic sentences². The effectiveness of source synthesis was considered, assessing whether sources were integrated through simple agreement, critical disagreement, or used to build towards a novel interpretation. The use of transitional phrases and signal words to evaluate the fluidity of logical connections between ideas and sections was also tracked through qualitative assessment.

¹ All 30 students did not commit to 4 essays each, leading to the mismatch in the total number of AI vs non-AI essays.

² The project team explained through the course of the experiment rounds, after the first set of essays were received, that topic sentences a) provide a topic focus to the paragraph and b) are subarguments [hence follow the argumentative structure of a thesis, having a what+why or a how]. We emphasised that ideally, the first sentence of the paragraph would identify a key idea or piece of evidence that the rest of the paragraph would deepen.

iv) Academic tone and style: general avoidance of colloquial language and contractions

Parallel to this, a qualitative analysis was conducted by prompting an LLM with 2 prompts, outlining the same four metrics in bullet point form with no overlapping instructions (**see Appendix B for the full prompt**).

Although a more detailed multi-shot prompting scenario could yield greater precision, and is the usage norm on average for students as well, time constraints limited this stage to a single comprehensive prompt.

B. Quantitative Scoring

Each essay received a cumulative score out of 12 corresponding to the 4 evaluative criteria above. These scores allowed for quantitative comparison alongside qualitative evaluation. They were used to train a classification model for argument mapping, in order to align CWC's established assessment model for correlating metrics with perceived writing strength.

C. Word-level Quantitative Analyses

Detailed word-by-word analyses were applied to essays across the following metrics:

- Lexical diversity index (unique words ÷ total words).
- Frequency of first-person pronouns.
- Analytical verb density.
- Hedging language frequency.
- Modal verb ratio.
- Frequency of assumption-indicating words.

Essays were benchmarked against libraries of analytical verbs ("Advises", "Advocates", "Affects", etc.), hedging terms (perhaps", "possibly", "arguably", "probably", and so on), first-person pronouns, and strong/weak modal verbs. For a more in-depth discussion of the quantitative rubric from which these metrics are drawn, see the section on Quantitative Rubric below, and review the Python code files having the full libraries.

D. Structural and Argument Mapping

This phase comprised a two-part LLM-based approach:

I. Unsupervised structure extraction

ChatGPT was prompted to annotate every sentence in a given sample by a specific function—context-setting, claim, evidence, citation, reasoning, and conclusion/stakes; determined solely by the LLM without any prior training data.

II. Semi-supervised annotation training

To refine the classifications, the LLM was trained using five expert-annotated samples of approximately 500-750 words representing the following disciplines:

- Political Science/History: A paper on *China's Bureaucratic Capitalism*
- Sociology/History: A paper on *Ambedkar and Caste*
- History/Architecture: A paper on the *Architecture of the Supreme Court*
- Sociology/Cultural Studies: A paper on *Placemaking in Modernity*
- English Literature: A paper on *Infrastructures in a Speculative Fiction Novel*

Each sentence in the samples was manually annotated to denote a function in argumentative writing: context-setting, claim, evidence, interpretation, citation, or significance-stating conclusion. These annotations were used to prompt the LLM for better sentence-level classification.

Interdisciplinary training samples enabled comparisons across writing conventions in the humanities and social sciences. The annotation process also accounted for overlapping rhetorical functions in SSH writing. For example, sentences simultaneously served as evidence and interpretation, or as context setting rather than explicit claims. Annotations across team members were not perfectly uniform, but they were generally streamlined to align with the shared model of argumentative writing.

Expert-provided annotations broadly aligned with those generated by the LLM in the first round. Based on these sentence-level annotations, the argument structures for **25** essays were analysed, and two sets of argument graphs were created. LLM-generated graphs illustrating relationships between individual sentences in a given essay. This visualisation type captures both sequential links (sentence 1 → sentence 2) and non-sequential dependencies (sentence 1→sentence 5), mapping the internal cohesion of a text.

The final set of graphs modelled logical relationships between higher-order argumentative components such as claim, evidence, thesis, and conclusion.

Together, these graphs were used to test whether essays produced with AI exhibit a higher degree of homogeneity and relatively rigid organisational patterns compared to those written without any AI support.

3.4 What is Argumentation?

To define and quantify argumentative writing for the purpose of this project, we began by acknowledging argumentation as a social process rather than a purely logical, formulaic one. Writers construct artefacts of reason to articulate and justify a central claim or explanation.

One synthesises evidence, engages critically with existing scholarship, and persuades readers through reasoned analysis rather than emotional appeal. Argumentation is distinguished by its reliance on relevant, well-chosen evidence to support a series of logically connected claims that deepen or draw back to a central thesis.

Arguments arise in situations of ambiguity, where more certainty is sought through persuasion. Arguments are oriented towards an audience and serve to clarify positions, defend beliefs, solve problems, or make judgments. Crucially, an argument presupposes disagreement or uncertainty; it does not occur where consensus already exists.

Unlike formal logic, which is context-independent and not aimed at persuasion, argumentation depends on context, audience adaptation, and credibility. While argument proceeds logically, it cannot be reduced to logic alone. An effective argument balances clarity of reasoning with an awareness of rhetorical situations and audience response.

Besides claims, reasons and support in the form of evidence, arguments also implicitly include warrants; the underlying assumptions that make the reasons persuasive. For instance, if one argues that *a liberal education improves critical thinking*, the implicit warrant is that *critical thinking is valuable*. Though we did not extract or assess warrants directly, we encouraged students to interrogate the underlying logic of a given phenomenon. During orientation, for example, we discussed how prompts like “*How is AI being used in policing in modern society?*” required interpretive attention to terms such as *policing* and *modern society*.

The context of the experiment was equally significant; students’ linguistic and cognitive attunement to argumentation depended on their stage of language acquisition and disciplinary exposure. Several participants were ESL learners who often struggled to place interpretive pressure on ideas due to limited vocabulary or disciplinary grounding. Consequently, their essays turned out to be descriptive rather than analytical.

A broader pedagogical challenge stems from pre-college writing instruction in India, where writing is treated primarily as a tool to “prove that they know” rather than “show how they know.” The dominant structure—introduction, body, and conclusion—often results in formulaic essays where the conclusion mirrors the introduction, and body paragraphs remain descriptive, summarising content rather than building independent arguments. Moreover, sustained writing tasks are rare in exam-driven curricula, which further limits students’ exposure to argumentative reasoning.

Given this background, quantifying argumentation poses a methodological challenge: they cannot be captured through standardised linguistic metrics alone. For instance, a high score on a Citation-to-Text Synthesis Ratio (CTR) might reflect effective use of sources, but cannot distinguish between essays that build original interpretations and those that merely echo existing scholarship.

3.5 How to quantify the argumentative structure and quality of an essay?

Quantifying argumentation requires a framework that recognises its complex and

multidimensional nature. Purely quantitative approaches risk reducing a nuanced intellectual exercise to decontextualised data points. Therefore, quantitative metrics must be interpreted alongside qualitative insights. Our quantitative framework was geared towards measuring sentence type frequency and distribution. Each essay was mapped into an argumentation graph derived from claims and the reasoning they contained.

This approach draws on literature in computational argumentation, where arguments are represented as graphs of interconnected nodes reflecting logical and rhetorical relationships (Somasundaran, 2016; Marro 2022). Argument components (claims, reasons, evidence, introduction, conclusion) function as nodes, and the relationships between them serve as edges, collectively forming a structured network of reasoning. While the model presented by Somasundaran et al. utilises individual content words (4+ characters long) as nodes without lemmatisation or synonym grouping, our method instead treats each sentence as a node, scaling up the unit of reasoning. This method not only models reasoning architecture but also reveals instances where LLM-generated annotations diverge from expert-substantiated rhetorical moves, highlighting both points of alignment as well as failure in machine interpretation.

In well-developed arguments, graphs display dense clusters of nodes, where detailed examples or elaborations are linked back to central claims, and each paragraph contains a coherent developmental arc: introducing, expanding, and concluding a point before shifting focus. In underdeveloped arguments, graphs are sparse with few nodes and weak interconnections, with subclaims often lacking evidence or failing to link back to the main thesis.

From these graphs, quantitative features were extracted to serve as proxies for argumentative quality. We selected three metrics evaluating the argument's density and focus. The first is the share of the argument's nodes that link back to the central claim. For example, if an essay consists of a series of disparate claims that don't build to a central argument, the maximum path of connected nodes on the graph would be low. This maximum path length therefore measures the claims and evidence worked into the central thesis.

Another metric we calculate is the average degree of the graph. This simply measures how many connections each node has on average, or how densely interconnected the student's argument is. If the thesis is established via many separate sub-chains of argument, the average degree should be low. On the other hand, if all the claims connect to each other cohesively and the cited evidence supports them mutually, the average degree should be very high. Finally, the ratio of nodes representing evidence to those representing claims is an important indicator of the student's focus. A low ratio combined with a high number of claims indicates that the student introduced a lot of ideas into the essay but without citation or support. A high ratio similarly indicates that the student grounded each claim with sufficient evidence from the relevant literature.

These metrics allow us to measure the quality of the argument while taking into account underlying features of the essay beyond just the patterns in the student's writing style. This is complemented by an assessment of the argumentation graphs, a much more comprehensive measure of the way the student's words translate into persuasive rhetoric, independent of their

command of language. Notably, every metric we calculated on the argumentation graphs showed negligible or insignificant results. Since the essays in our sample are extremely short this could reflect a lack of sufficient data or that AI assistance has no impact on students' argumentative essays.

3.6 Quantitative Rubrics

To complement the qualitative assessment, the project team designed quantitative measures to capture aspects of 3 broad domains: argumentation, language use, and claim-evidence integration. Specific metrics were designed to identify distinguishing markers between AI-assisted and human-authored essays in each of these 3 domains, and to quantify various measures of writing quality in the given essays.

Argumentation included 7 parameters related to contextualization, problematisation, argument development, and originality.

Language use included 9 parameters evaluating authorial presence, objectivity, and linguistic complexity, relying primarily on word-level counts.

Claim-evidence integration was measured through 7 metrics, and finally, logical integrity and coherence were measured through 4 parameters.

Domain	Metric	Definition/ Parameter	Interpretation
Argumentation	Contextualization Density (CD)	Contextualizing sentences ÷ total sentences	Measures grounding of argument in intellectual/historical frameworks
	Problematization Ratio (PR)	Critical questions ÷ total assertions	Indicates depth of interrogation of assumptions
	Theoretical Framework Engagement (TFE)	Theoretical references ÷ total paragraphs	Tracks use of theory to expand or problematise argument

Domain	Metric	Definition/ Parameter	Interpretation
Argumentation	Argument Development Density (ADD)	New sub-claims ÷ total words	Quantifies dynamism and multi-layered reasoning
	Depth of Reasoning Score (DRS)	Scaled 1 (descriptive)–5 (critical insight)	Rates interpretive depth
	Cohesion vs. Novelty Metric (CNM)	New contributions ÷ cited contributions	Captures originality vs. reliance on existing literature
	Intertextual Reference Frequency (IRF)	Intertextual references ÷ total words	Measures comparative synthesis of sources
Language Use	First-Person Pronoun Frequency (FPF)	First-person pronouns ÷ total words	Indicates authorial voice
	Authorial Comment Density (ACD)	Subjective interpretations ÷ total words	Measures interpretive presence
	Modal Verb Ratio (MVR)	Assertive ÷ tentative modals	Gauges confidence in argumentation
	Hedging Language Frequency (HLF)	Tentative words ÷ total words	Reflects cautious or speculative tone
	Lexical Diversity Index (LDI)	Unique words ÷ total words	Captures vocabulary range and originality

Domain	Metric	Definition/ Parameter	Interpretation
Language Use	Variety Index (VI)	Distinct sentence structures ÷ total sentences	Measures syntactic variation
	Disciplinary Term Count (DTC)	Domain-specific terms ÷ total words	Tracks disciplinary precision
	Passive Voice Ratio (PVR)	Passive sentences ÷ total sentences	Indicates stylistic control/formality
	Analytical Verb Density (AVD)	Analytical verbs ÷ total verbs	Reflects argumentative precision
Claim-Evidence Integration	Primary Evidence Citation Frequency (PSCFW)	Primary sources ÷ 1000 words	Measures empirical grounding
	Secondary Evidence Citation Frequency (SSCFW)	Secondary sources ÷ 1000 words	Measures engagement with literature
	PS/SS Citation Ratio (PS/SSCR)	Primary ÷ secondary citations	Indicates balance between data and theory
	Citation-to-Text Synthesis Ratio (CTR)	Citations supporting claims ÷ total citations	Gauges effectiveness of evidence use
	Evidence-to-Hypothesis Ratio (EHR)	Evidence sentences ÷ hypothesis statements	Tests logical alignment of claims

Domain	Metric	Definition/ Parameter	Interpretation
Claim- Evidence Integration	Comparative Synthesis Ratio (CSR)	Comparative ÷ descriptive statements	Captures analytical synthesis
	Evidence Support Percentage (ESP)	Paragraphs linking evidence to thesis ÷ total paragraphs	Measures argumentative cohesion
Logical Integrity & Coherence	Focus Score (FS)	Single-idea paragraphs ÷ total paragraphs	Tests structural focus
	Coherence Density Ratio (CDR)	Related ideas ÷ total ideas	Quantifies logical connection
	Transition Link Count (TLC)	Explicit connectors ÷ total sentences	Measures flow between ideas
	Paraphrase-to- Quote Ratio (PQR)	Paraphrased sources ÷ quoted sources	Indicates depth of source engagement

P-values were calculated for all metrics mentioned above after comparing per-metric values for AI-assisted and non-AI text. The statistically significant indicators were: **Lexical Diversity Index (LDI)**, **First-Person Pronoun Frequency (FPF)**, **Authorial Comment Density (ACD)**, and **Evidence-to-Hypothesis Ratio (EHPR)**.

4. FINDINGS

This section covers 3 aspects: i) a discussion of the statistically significant metrics for assessing writing in samples with the presence or absence of AI use, ii) on argument structures reflected in student writing based on argument graphs, and iii) typifying participants' engagement with AI in the course of the experiments.

4.1 Impact on Authorial Voice

There were several statistically significant differences between writing produced with AI assistance and without, across both groups of students (ELT students and non-ELT students). This points to a distinct shift in rhetorical and substantive qualities when it comes to writing with vs without AI.

Figure 1: Smoothed density plot of the frequency of first-person pronouns in essays by students with and without AI, sample size = 71

The Y axis in Fig. 1 above represents probability density. The height of the curve indicates how densely concentrated essays are around that range of values. The total area under each curve equals “1”, regardless of how many essays are in each group (AI-assisted vs non-AI). A smoothed density plot has been selected since this visualisation normalises the distribution, allowing for a direct comparison of AI-assisted and non-AI writing—this is important because sample sizes differ in this case.

In Fig. 1, we observe that AI-assisted essays peak at higher FPF values signalling a surface-level increase in the writer's presence via first-person pronouns, whereas non-AI writing shows a lower,

tighter concentration. At the same time, there is a significant area overlap under the curves, indicating that this metric does not meaningfully distinguish between AI-assisted and non-AI writing in that range. For AI-assisted writing, there is a certain standardised presence of individual “voice” via first-person pronouns, but this does not necessarily signal particularly reflective framing.

AI assisted writing tends to show a higher presence of first-person pronouns than writing that does not use AI.

This is further exemplified by the graph on Authorial Comment Density in AI-assisted vs non-AI writing.

Figure 2: Smoothed density plot of the frequency of authorial comments in essays by students with and without AI available, sample size = 71

In Fig. 2, AI-assisted writing shows a sharp spike near lower ACD values; the narrow curve indicates a greater consistency in the AI-assisted dataset. The majority of essays using AI cluster around zero authorial comments, such as anecdotes and analogies linked to analytical commentary. The longer tail in the non-AI curve indicates that there is greater heterogeneity in how writers intervene in their texts and stronger trend of stylistic idiosyncrasy in human-only writing samples. As before, AI seems to produce a homogenising effect on structural parameters related to authorial presence.

In non-AI essays, authorial comments frequently perform multiple, and sometimes overlapping, functions. They may appear as anecdote-as-hook, anecdote-as-example, assumption, or critique. For instance, one participant uses an authorial comment as a hook in service of an argument: *“Imagine a company today—maybe a giant tech corporation—slowly expanding its influence*

until it starts controlling entire countries". The comment functions rhetorically to establish resonance with the contemporary moment to then introduce an argument on the East India Company in the 1600s. The impulse behind using this anecdote is not simply decorative but rather scaffolding a conceptual *transfer* between historical moments.

In another case, a participant writes that they believe "women are differentiated from the past generation in terms of education, personal life, career, being independent, and so on", when evaluating the relevance of Virginia Woolf's *A Room of One's Own* in their contemporary present. The same writer then reinterprets a room as personal space in the Indian context after marriage. They observe that women returning to their natal homes may no longer have a room of their own, and instead occupy siblings' rooms. Though assumptive and anecdotal, the argumentative impulse behind this authorial comment is to gesture towards how women move between statuses—from family member to spouse to guest—often losing spatial autonomy along the way. The authorial comment mixes personal observation and normative judgement. ACD hence does not map neatly onto "effective" or "poor" writing; rather, it captures the presence of the writer's voice as they negotiate evidence, inference, and experience.

In contrast, some samples show authorial comments that are more diffuse, relying heavily on assumption, as in this writing sample by an ELT student: "From history we have heard that how britishers have trained our indian societies into developing one .They have made our agriculture more advanced with implementation of new technologies and also exchanges the cultural and tradition from us." The same essay includes more general statements linked to the same personal writing style: "...if we talk about economic adaptation so globalization is providing a global platform for competition and challenging complexities residing in our communities where people are really using it for embracing the new technologies , expanding the market and improving efficiencies". The author goes on to claim that globalisation paved the way for women workers' participation, signalling a bridge to the broader assertion that globalisation changes the encounter with "tradition". While the writing sample lacks evidence or citation to anchor these claims, certain authorial comments reference points that recur throughout the essay.

In AI-assisted essays, the range of ACD is significantly lower (0.04–0.07) as compared to non-AI writing. The essay scoring 0.07 co-occurs with higher net score (out of 12) and non-ELT status. Consider the following example: "With this essay, I hope to probe into behavioural shifts and inversions of self-perception with the advent of optimisation culture...". In this and the sentences that follow, ACD functions as argumentative framing. The authorial voice explicitly declares research intent, defines "optimisation culture," and outlines its implications, but does not reference personal experience.

These examples suggest that ACD is a polysemic indicator and should be interpreted contextually rather than as a simple linear proxy for argumentative quality.

The higher presence of first-person pronouns in AI-assisted writing is coupled with lower presence of authorial comments, regularising the "structure" we expect to find in AI-assisted outputs as compared to non-AI writing, where the presence of authorial idiosyncrasies is more explicit.

4.2 Impact on Lexical Diversity

Figure 3: Smoothed density plot and histogram of the lexical diversity index of essays by students with and without AI available, sample size = 71

Analysis of the lexical diversity index (LDI) in Fig. 3 above indicates a rightward shift of the curve in the distribution of AI-assisted essays, with peak density occurring at higher LDI values with peak density occurring at higher LDI values compared to non-AI writing.

The histogram shows a greater concentration of AI-assisted essays in the upper LDI range, while non-AI essays cluster more strongly around mid-range values. Though the difference in LDI is statistically significant, the substantial overlap between the distributions shows that many non-AI essays achieve comparable levels of lexical diversity. This suggests that AI assistance shifts the distribution upwards rather than expanding or redefining the overall bounds of lexical diversity.

Given the short length of essays (approx. 500 words each), higher LDI should not necessarily be interpreted as evidence of more domain-specific vocabulary. Instead, it reflects a lower degree of word reuse. However, strategic repetition of key terms often plays an important role in reinforcing central claims and clarifying the thesis. For example, in a non-AI essay, a student uses "male gaze" in the thesis and then expands upon it in reference to womens' sexuality, and references to inter-character friendships in the following paragraph. These references are used to develop into subarguments about subversive sexualities and womens' friendships.

The pattern reflected in the dataset is consistent with how large language models generate text: through probabilistically favouring variation and avoiding repetition. In the essays written by students in the cohort with lower English proficiency, AI functions as a synonymising and phrasing tool. While LDI increases in this process, it may dilute the deliberate reuse of conceptually important terms unique to the writer's framing, especially in structurally significant areas like topic sentences.

AI-assisted writing shows a rightward-shifted distribution, with the peak density occurring at higher LDI values. Non-AI essays cluster more strongly in the mid-range. While the difference in LDI is statistically significant, the substantial overlap between the curves demonstrates that many non-AI essays achieve comparable lexical diversity. AI use appears to shift the distribution of lexical diversity upwards rather than redefining its bounds.

4.3 Impact on Evidence-Hypothesis

Figure 4: Smoothed density plot and histogram of the ratio of evidence to claims in essays by students with and without AI available, sample size = 71

Another significant difference among essays written with AI assistance was the proportion of the essay devoted to making claims, versus supporting them with reasoning and evidence. AI-assisted essays displayed a substantially lower Evidence-to-Hypothesis Ratio (E/HPR), indicating that students using AI focused much more on making claims than elaborating on them with paragraphs of explanation or evidence. Non-AI essays display a wider distribution with a longer tail, reflecting a broader range of evidentiary practices: from low support to more developed, evidence-rich arguments; and importantly, potentially more diverse argumentative strategies. One implication of this pattern is that AI-assisted writing may encourage more moderated, flattened, or descriptive forms of writing with predictable sentence structures. For example, a number of AI-assisted samples show 3-part evidence statements, eg: “However, some small business owners later reported negative effects, such as reducing employee hours, freezing hiring, and even laying off workers.”, “In democratic regimes, liberalism promotes the right to speech, the right to choose among multiple political parties, and rules that restrict the power of the Government”. This type of writing summarises a position rather than developing or critiquing it. Precise references to text or empirical details are sparse. These “overview-style” constructions provide an appearance of range and fluency, leading to a spike in metrics such as LDI³.

³ Marcus Olenq identifies this three-part structure as “a direct linguistic descendant of the British Empire.” He argues that these highly formalised sentence structures were overrepresented in LLM training data, leading the outputs to amplify these existing patterns as normative, due to which ChatGPT sounds like him rather than the other way around. Other scholarship, such as this paper by Fleisig et al. note that when GPT-3.5 Turbo and GPT-4 are asked to imitate the writing style of prompts in non-“standard” varieties, they produce text that exhibits lower comprehension of the input and is especially prone to stereotyping.

Besides these results, many of the metrics that we measured yielded non-significant effects with small effect sizes. These included measures of originality (Cohesion vs Novelty Metric), writing style (Passive Voice Ratio, Analytical Verb Density, Hedging Language Frequency), synthesis ability (Citation-to-Text Ratio, Intertextual Reference Frequency, Comparative Synthesis Ratio), and critical engagement (Contextualization Density, Problematization Ratio). This partly points towards AI-assistance not significantly changing every aspect of student writing, but this is also shaped by the nature and quality of the samples. Most essays contain few or no instances of students critically engaging with theoretical frameworks or problematisation of existing views. Similarly, 500-word essays are short enough that many indicators are absent altogether or only present in one or two sentences per essay. Many essays include no citations whatsoever or have no sentences in the passive voice. AI assistance does not significantly increase the presence of these markers—this could indicate that students who use LLMs primarily see changes in their grammar and writing style rather than any meaningful logical or structural improvements. However, a larger, longer-term dataset with multiple rounds of revision and qualitative insights from participants would be required to validate this intuition.

4.4 Impact on Argument Structure

While these metrics signal the differences in writing style, they provide a limited understanding of the way the essay is structured. To better understand sample structures, one can examine the properties of the nodes (claims and reasoning) and edges (argument flow) of the argumentation graphs derived from each essay. In order to create argument graphs, each sentence in a student sample was annotated for a specific purpose served, such as “context”, “reasoning”, “citation”, “evidence”, and “claim”. **See the spreadsheet titled “Argument Graph Metrics” and the code files to see how these were calculated and the relevant values.** These annotations were generated by an LLM, and cross-referenced with expert annotations from five expert-written samples in order to validate the LLM classifications. Despite this, several sentences annotated in the student samples do not align with expert-annotator interpretation. This is because of the difference in inter-annotator agreement and classifications (which were not normalised for this round of analysis), as well as expert training samples being fairly advanced so as not to have sentences marked as “hedging” or “assumptions”. Expert samples also provided more than one annotation per sentence, whereas LLM annotations only provided one annotation per sentence. This is a significant limitation of this study.

LLM-annotated student samples were then rewritten by an LLM to track only 3 properties (claim, evidence, thesis statement); sentences that might have been annotated ambiguously by human classifiers were singularly categorised in one of the three. This yielded a set of thesis statements (1 per sample), as well as multiple claims and evidence-sentences per sample, and relationships between these “synthesised” outputs were then graphed. Argument graphs were developed for 25 essays - 13 essays written without AI, comprising 8 essays by ELT students and 5 by non-ELT students, and 12 essays written with AI, comprising 7 by ELT students and 5 by non-ELT students.

Fig 5: No. of students writing with and without AI disaggregated by ELT status

Two metrics were calculated for each graph: a) the “degree” (number of connections between claims and reasoning in the essay), and b) the maximum path length (longest chain of interconnected ideas).

Essays written without AI assistance exhibited substantially greater dispersion in average degree (≈ 2.2 to 3.6) and maximum path length (3 to 8). This heterogeneity reflects the natural diversity of rhetorical strategies used by students when responding to an argumentative essay prompt without standardised assistance.

In contrast, AI-assisted essays are more tightly clustered around similar structural values (Avg. degree mostly ≈ 2.0 – 2.8 ; path length mostly ≈ 3 – 5), suggesting a homogenising effect in the way the arguments are *organised*. AI usage appears to compress structural differences between ESL and non-ESL writers, producing essays that are more similar to each other in terms of argumentative “connectivity” than essays written without AI. However, this does not directly correlate to argumentative sophistication or overall “score” out of 12 indicating the quality of writing.

Essays written by ELT students and/or with AI assistance tended, on average, to have shorter maximum path lengths. With regard to a time-constrained context when students are required to write only about 500 words, shorter path lengths do not necessarily denote any deficiency when it comes to argumentative strength. Preliminary examination shows that low maximum path length (3–4) appears frequently among lower- and mid-scoring essays, especially among ESL and AI-assisted entries. Moderate path lengths sometimes occur alongside high scores, suggesting non-linearity rather than a simple negative correlation. Higher scores tend to coincide with moderate-to-high average degree (≈ 2.6 – 3.6), rather than much lower degree values. That being said, some

high-scoring essays do have shorter path lengths, but these are not the dominant case; many high scores cluster around path lengths of 5-8.

Fig 6: Correlation Heatmap of Essay Metrics, where ratio is calculated as the following: no. of evidence sentences/ no. of claims sentences + No. of thesis sentences (1 per essay) and grade indicates manually provided score out of 12.

Fig. 6 shows pairwise correlations between four essay metrics: average degree, maximum path length, ratio, and grade. The numbers within each cell indicate correlation coefficients ranging from -1 to +1, and the colours convey the strength and direction of correlation—red indicating positive correlation and blue indicating negative correlation. Darker colours signal stronger relationships. Fig. 6 above shows that avg_degree and max_path_length show a moderately strong positive correlation (=0.58). However, both these metrics show weak negative correlations with grade (-0.37 and -0.05 respectively) implying that a higher number of connections or longer writing samples do not reliably translate into higher marks.

The ratio measure is negatively correlated with all other variables, most strongly with grade (-0.47).

4.5 Does AI-Assistance Improve Student Essays?

Since the release of ChatGPT in 2022, and the widespread availability of consumer LLMs, schoolwork and college essays have become one of the most popular use-cases for text generation. There is also generally a perception that this is a negative development, for two reasons: first, that the student “outsources” the work without going through the gradual process of learning, which entails trial-and-error and gradual refinement, and second, that the writer fails to critically engage with the research material.

The essays written by participants were evaluated on the four parameters given earlier: Introduction, Claims & Evidence, Argument Structure, and Academic Style. The average scores assigned to students using AI assistance were significantly higher than those of students without AI access. Among non-AI essays, the mean score was 4.8/12, with each component ranging from 1.1 to 1.3 out of 3. Among essays written with AI assistance, the mean score was 6.5, with each component ranging from 1.5 to 1.7. AI-assisted essays were assigned significantly higher scores for Style and Structure, albeit with little improvement on these scores among students already proficient in English (non-ELT students in our categorisation).

The overall quality of these essay samples is quite low. Several essays have grammatical errors, run-on sentences, and flawed argumentation. The task of formulating a thesis, marshaling evidence, and structuring a logical progression of ideas within a 500-word, one-hour limit is a significant challenge for a substantial portion of the undergraduate population. However, regardless of the quality of the essays, it is clear that grading essays is dependent not only on argumentative strength; grammatically clean, well-organised, and coherent essays will naturally be at an advantage. These are immediate areas that LLMs can help students with, translating neatly into the improvement in essay scores. This indicates a potential misalignment between the stated learning objectives of argumentative writing, which emphasises critical thinking and evidence-based reasoning, and the practical metrics that actually influence grades. AI usage in this set of essays, in effect, is geared towards optimising for visible signals of quality that are most easily achievable and most efficiently assessed (the more deterministic metrics), rather than the more ambivalent and time consuming metrics related to analytical rigour.

Consequently, in the specific context of short essays written under a time constraint, AI assistance appears to function less as a substitute for, or a supplement for argumentation, and more as a simple grammar and writing aid. The improvement in scores may not reflect a necessarily well-written argument, but perhaps a more legible and familiar one. The challenge for educators is to re-evaluate whether the assignment itself effectively cultivates and assesses the intended skills, or if it has inadvertently prioritised a form of compositional fluency that AI can now readily supply.

4.6 Analysing Essays Written by ELT students

Figure 7: Smoothed density plot and histogram of the grades (out of 12) assigned to essays by students with and without AI available, sample size = 71

The distribution of essay scores suggests that AI assistance does not uniformly “improve” student writing in the sense of shifting all students toward higher performance, but it does appear to reshape the performance distribution, particularly for ELT students. The ELT curve is more tightly concentrated around lower values, peaking at a significantly lower essay score than that of non-

ELT students (density plot). In the histogram, the absolute scores are majorly between 0 and 5 out of 12. At the same time, the substantial overlap between the two distributions in the density plot indicates that AI does not eliminate underlying differences in writing proficiency. Moreover, the non-ELT distribution retains a longer right tail, implying that higher levels of performance are still more frequently achieved by students with stronger baseline proficiency, even with AI available. Taken together, the figure suggests that AI functions less as a tool for elevating all writing to a higher level and more as a stabilising mechanism, narrowing performance gaps without necessarily fostering the conditions for exceptional writing.

Figure 8: Box plot of the grades (out of 12) assigned to essays by English-native and ESL students with and without AI available, sample size = 71

The boxplot compares the distribution of essay scores for ELT and non-ELT students, disaggregated by the availability of AI assistance. The area in blue and brown indicate the range of 50% of the distribution of marks, also known as the interquartile range. The “whiskers” or the topmost and bottom-most marks in the chart show the full distribution. Finally, the median mark is represented by the horizontal line in the blue and brown boxes.

Across both groups, essays written with AI assistance show a higher median score than those written without AI, with the median being greatly amplified in the ELT cohort. Among non-ELT students, AI-assisted essays not only have a higher median but also a wider interquartile range and higher upper values, indicating greater variability alongside improved *central* tendency. For ELT students, AI assistance appears to raise the median score modestly while also extending the upper range significantly, suggesting that some students benefit substantially from AI support, even as overall variability remains pronounced.

As for the non-ELT cohort, there was a small increase in scores across every component, with the largest being a 60% bump in the Introduction component mean score (1.14 to 1.86). Among ELT students, however, scores rose by a larger amount across the board, with differing areas of emphasis. The largest improvement among them was on the Style component, aligning with our previous analysis. The mean Style score doubled from 0.83 without AI, to 1.66 with AI available. AI availability closed almost the entirety of the gap in Style scores between English-native and ESL students, while also reducing the disparity on all other components.

The minor improvements in Claims and Structure scores across the board indicate that AI helps students organise their ideas into a more recognisable academic format, which is useful for students with less training in academic writing.

Figure 9: Box plot of the grades (out of 3) assigned to essay introductions by English-native and ESL students with and without AI available, sample size = 71

Another point of interest is that the Introduction component defies the trend in both groups of students. The Introduction component was the only component on which ESL students received a

higher score, on average, than non-ELT students. Further analyses are required to establish causal relationships in this regard.

Interestingly, however, the gap between the Introduction scores of the two groups widens when AI assistance is available. Without AI, non-ELT students are judged to have slightly worse introductions (1 for non-ELT students vs 1.25 for ELT students). With AI available, these introductory sections become perceived as substantially more effective, while the previously higher-scored introductions by ELT students fare significantly worse. This could point towards differences in the way writing assistants are used by students of different groups; but tracking these specific differences in prompting styles and points of intervention for ELT vs non-ELT students requires further analysis. Reliable analysis with the available dataset is difficult since a large number of chatlogs could not be collected from participants, and total conversations with LLMs tended to be quite brief, even in instances where multiple LLMs are used.

4.7 How do Students Use LLMs for Argumentative Essays?

Using the recorded chat logs from the various LLMs used by the students writing with AI assistance, we can study exactly how the students engaged with the chatbot during the writing process. Each log was manually parsed and each high-level phase of the writing process - research, writing, and editing - was attributed to either the human, or the chatbot. In cases where the two worked together to write or iterate on the essay, we tagged the usage as a “collaboration”.

Figure 10: Bar graph showing modes of engagement between students and AI. The majority of types place AI in a central role.

No ELT student in the available set of chatlogs used the LLM as a collaborator in any of the three processes. Among non-ELT students, 3 individuals used AI as a collaborator for writing. ELT

students tended to use much shorter prompts with fewer instructions, and also did not cross-question the LLM outputs as much as compared to non-ELT students.

These differences indicate that the AI's utility is heavily mediated by the user's pre-existing writing proficiency and familiarity with LLM tools. In this case, the LLM serves primarily as a compensation tool for ELT students, masking foundational weaknesses in grammar and argumentative structure without necessarily fostering a deeper understanding of the material or the process of argumentation (Bekker, 2024).

This creates a potential area of concern: while LLM assistance narrows the gap in superficial presentation, it may inadvertently widen the gap between students by side-stepping the learning process. It is questionable whether the purported use of LLMs to provide scaffolding for the intellectual work of argument framing is reflected in the actual real-world usage of such tools - particularly by the students who are furthest behind in the development of these skills.

Notably, there is no instance where students use AI to edit independently researched writing—they either used the AI to provide research and ideas before writing entirely on their own (often paraphrasing the information provided by the LLM), or had AI generate the entire essay.

The latter approach represents the common, concerning phenomenon of students outsourcing cognitive, learning-intensive labour to LLMs entirely. In nearly half the essays, which were accompanied by chat logs in our sample (6/14), the LLM generated the entire body of the text, with the human contributing few or no edits to the final essay. This “copy-paste” phenomenon reflects the harm of LLMs being used as student replacements in real-life academic evaluations. It is clear that, when given the option, many students opt to skip the process of writing entirely and simply submit the LLM’s output, with little regard for learning or verifying the content.

5. CONCLUSION

The report situates the rapid integration of generative AI into academic writing within the broader trajectory of the rise of large language models since late 2022, foregrounding both the affordances and challenges of their widespread adoption. Drawing on existing scholarship and institutional experience at the Centre for Writing and Communication, Ashoka University, it underscores how AI tools are being used across stages of learning and writing for purposes ranging from concept clarification and language refinement to idea generation and structural support. At the same time, the literature and consultation-based observations point to significant concerns, particularly the risks of overreliance, diminished cognitive engagement, and the incorporation of inaccuracies and biases. These tensions highlight the need to examine AI use not only through ethical or regulatory lenses but through everyday academic practice, especially in spaces such as writing centres that prioritise sustained, reflective engagement with writing.

Against this backdrop, the experimental study detailed in the report examines the impact of AI assistance on argumentative academic writing through a controlled, comparative design. By analysing essays written with and without AI support across clearly defined parameters and by closely examining student-LLM interaction logs, the study sheds light on how students actually engage with these tools and how such engagement shapes argumentative quality, structure, and style. The findings point to patterns of use that often prioritise efficiency over learning, including instances of full outsourcing of writing to LLMs, raising questions about the pedagogical value of such practices. In focusing on these dynamics within the context of South Asian higher education, the report seeks to contribute to ongoing debates on the responsible integration of generative AI, to identify practices that preserve the rigour of academic composition while recognising the realities of algorithmic augmentation.

In this project, we have approached AI-supported academic writing practice from a rhetoric and composition perspective. Writing centre members are uniquely positioned to lead an inquiry like this, working routinely across disciplines and genres while being situated in particular subjects themselves, and so being able to comment not only on correctness or output, but also on how arguments are built, revised, and move between contexts. By mapping existing feedback categories onto a specific set of analytically tractable parameters, we hope for this study to provide a framework through which other practitioners, faculty, and students can systematically assess and improve the integration of AI in academic writing. We hope that this project can give rise to guidelines that serve this common goal.

At the same time, we are attentive to impacts beyond academic performance or efficiency. In our day-to-day work with students, we encounter issues such as algorithmic bias—gendered, cultural, and linguistic—and the risk that AI systems may reproduce or even amplify them. An exploratory experiment conducted by the team, where AI generated a deeply biased framing of caste as “spiritual”, underlined the stakes of students outsourcing reading and interpretation to chatbots. If students rely on AI to mediate reading, what is lost is not merely information, but also the development of critical judgement about what is worth reading and how it should be read. Writing centres, situated close to both curriculum and student experiences of it, are therefore well placed to

assess what students actually engage with, what they are likely to skip, and how AI may subtly reshape these choices, especially in areas where the readings themselves are about bias and inequity.

We are equally attentive to shifts in authorial voice and questions of ownership. The dilution of voice where a piece of writing could have been written by “anyone” is not only a matter of plagiarism, but is consequential in applications and professional writing. Practitioners need ways to talk with students about how AI can both support and erode the development of a distinctive voice. Relatedly, transparency and disclosure around AI use remain complex: when AI assistance is woven into the drafting process with multiple rounds of revision, students are often unsure how to acknowledge it, and instructors may struggle to form a holistic sense of their students’ labour and learning. Writing centres can be central in this instance, to helping students articulate not only *what* they wrote, but *how* they wrote it.

Concerns about hallucination, privacy, and the ethics of data collection and *creation* likewise sit at the heart of writing centre pedagogy. Many of our team members come from disciplines where fieldwork and research with human participants are core, and so questions of responsibility to research subjects, consent, and risk are already part of their intellectual training. This attunement carries over into conversations about AI, especially in encounters with students whose work focuses on primary data and fieldwork.

Limitations and future directions

We faced several limitations in the process of conducting this study. Only 71 essays were considered for analysis, representing a small sample size whose findings might not generalize to all student writing. Additionally, all the students under study were drawn from a limited pool of primarily undergraduate students at a single liberal arts university, which affects external validity. While conducting the study, technical failures resulted in chat logs from only 18 essays being available for analysis. Consequently, we are unable to make empirical claims about the way in which students engaged with the LLMs in the process of writing. Additionally, several metrics that have been widely used in literature couldn’t be used for our analysis because of the constraints of the samples. For example, citation ratios and the use of intertextual or primary versus secondary evidence couldn’t be analysed because most essays cited no sources, especially intertextual or primary sources.

Despite clear instructions in the experiment orientation to the contrary, few essays showed critical engagement with theoretical frameworks or problematisation of existing views/literature. Given the 500-word limit, many indicators outlined in the methodology are either absent or very sparse, and they could not be used to show statistically significant differences in non-AI vs. AI-assisted writing. A larger dataset, longer essays, repeated drafts, and qualitative accounts from students to assess self-reported AI use are important to validate if and how AI contributes to conceptual development in the learning process. Future work should also investigate the correlations between each textual metric and the scores, as was done with argument graphs. Inter-annotator consistency should be established in the process of manual scoring prior to analysis.

Having longer writing samples may allow us to interrogate and establish higher-order relationships among claims, examples, and reasoning. We may investigate graph-based metrics such as node centrality (e.g., PageRank) to capture the hierarchical importance of core claims clustering coefficients to measure the cohesion of developed examples, and the ratio of edge weights to assess the strength of connections between premises and conclusions. Given the short length of samples, these metrics did not yield clearly interpretable or discriminative patterns.

Another important direction to expand in is testing the bounds of LLM-driven assessment. In the process of manual qualitative analysis, where marks were assigned to train a classifier to identify sentence annotations such as “evidence” and “claim”, the project team had ChatGPT assess the participant samples with a detailed single-shot prompt. Further evaluation, comparing the accuracy, contextualisation, and patterns of critique in LLM-generated assessments versus human assessments, can be a next step in this inquiry.

Nevertheless, our current analysis represents a step forward in understanding the way that students use LLMs to augment their argumentation capabilities, and the impact this has on their writing output. Our finding that AI usage increases the perceived quality of a student’s essay, while potentially detracting from the value of writing it as a learning exercise, has concerning implications for the use of essay-writing in academic evaluation.

Additionally, our evidence that ESL students are unable to use LLMs as a collaborative partner to efficiently improve their argumentation provides a clear direction for future studies and intervention.

6. APPENDICES

A. Orientation Plan

AI Project Orientation

March- April 2025

CWC, Mphasis Lab

Neerav, Archishman, Sampurna

Part I: Primer on academic writing

1. Introduced the time split for the experiment, guidelines for academic writing, the experiment, Post workshop: signing participation sheet + queries, discussion if forthcoming

1. Experiment & expectations of academic writing outputs

- **Answer a prompt of your choice in 60 mins without using AI in 450-500 words.**

Write a structured response, including:

- **Introduction** (topic and thesis). A thesis ideally will have a “what” + “why/how”. Specific and arguable. Eg: “The Green Revolution was detrimental to Indian agriculture because it was anti-ecological.”
- Claims backed by evidence
- Ensure progression of arguments, counterpoints, supporting arguments, if any, and their relation to the principal argument (flow)
- **Write in an academic style** which entails avoiding informal conversational/informal tone/contractions/colloquialisms.
- You don’t need a title, unless you want to provide one.
- Conclusion: end with stakes or significance.

1. Quick look at the prompts

Many of the prompts are broad (e.g., *How is AI being used in policing in modern society?*). To refine your approach, consider the range of meanings behind terms like **"policing"** and **"modern society."**

- **Policing** can be of various kinds—from implicit surveillance that influences behaviour to explicit enforcement mechanisms like Delhi police controlling crowds.
-
- **Modern society** is also diverse: In Indian cities, mass migration is often informal and difficult to track, while in highly surveilled environments, data collection is far more granular.
-

To make your response more focused, ground it in specific examples. You can either explore a single case, such as **Beijing’s AI-driven policing**, or compare **two contexts** to examine how AI is deployed differently across urban settings.

1. Logins and wrapping up: You may log into your accounts (stuck to the wooden desk beside the monitor) if you prefer to use GDocs. Alternatively, you may use MS Word directly.

IMPORTANT: copy-paste your chat log into your doc, and provide the login/pw for your AI tool account assigned during this experiment IF you've changed it. Also share a live link to the chat wherever possible, and list the AI tools used in the writing experiment

Easy access to GDoc: type "docs.new" in browser

- Before you leave the lab, email your answer to, or share the link with cwcmphasisai2025@gmail.com; cc'ing neerav.dwivedi@ashoka.edu.in ; sampurna.dutta@ashoka.edu.in

Part 2: Writing with AI

- **Writing with AI Assistance**
- **Introduction (10 minutes):** Overview of AI tools and guidelines.
- Students were guided to select a prompt and write for 60 mins:
 - Use AI tools to brainstorm ideas, generate drafts, and refine responses.
 - You can ask AI-specific questions or request revisions.
- Guidelines for Prompt Engineering
- **Be specific with your topic:** Clearly state your research topic or question. For example, instead of asking, "Explain postcolonialism," ask, "How does Edward Said's concept of Orientalism inform postcolonial studies?" - Connecting the 'What' with 'How', 'When', 'Why', 'Where' will help sharpen your analysis.
- **Provide Context:** Briefly mention the background of your query, including referring to your course materials, to give a narrowed-down reference point. For instance, "I am exploring the impact of modernization theory in 20th-century development economics."
 -
- **Define the Scope:** Indicate whether you want an overview, a deep dive, or a comparison. Example: "Summarize the key arguments in related to surveillance."
- **Try not to stack several instructions within a single prompt.** - Use different prompts to add instructions - Give one instruction per prompt
- **Indicate the Level of Detail:** Clarify whether the response should be brief or comprehensive. Example: "In 200 words, explain the main differences between X and Y as it pertains to literary writing/ policy analysis"/ "Explain how Theory Y applies to contemporary policy debates"/

-
- “Summarize three key differences between System A and System B in governance.”/”Discuss the role of inflation in shaping economic policies over the past decade”
 - **Iterate for Refinement:** Use follow-up prompts to refine the initial response. Example: "Expand on the ecological dimensions of ..."/ “Describe two case studies where...”/”Provide real-world examples of...”/ “Explain the core principles of...”/ “Explain and analyse the causes and consequences”

3. Mention your objective/intention clearly at the levels of:

a. Motive of analysis

b. Writing style. For example, for a. Do you want a simple descriptive analysis or do you want to problematise the chosen topic?

And for b. If you want an argumentative tone—in terms of vocabulary usage—indicate that. You can use phrases such as ‘avoid contractions’/‘avoid colloquialisms’/ ‘avoid informal/conversational tone’

B. LLM Prompts for Qualitative Assessment

Prompt 1: Using the criteria listed below, provide a bullet-point commentary and critical analysis of the document:

1. Introduction – Assess how effectively the topic and central thesis are introduced.
2. Claims and Evidence – Evaluate the strength and relevance of the claims made and the quality of supporting evidence.
3. Argument Structure – Examine the logical flow of arguments, including the use of counterarguments and supporting points, and analyse how they contribute to or reinforce the main argument.
4. Academic Style – Ensure that the analysis is written in a formal academic style. Avoid conversational language, contractions, and colloquialisms.

Prompt 2: Using the same parameters, check for plagiarism.

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